

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

THE USE OF CRITERION-REFERENCED ASSESSMENT IN PHYSICS LESSONS AND ITS KEY FEATURES

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Abstract

The article examines one of the main reasons for the emergence of the issue of changing or updating the system of assessing the quality of education at the present stage, namely the contradictions between changing social demands, transformations in students' cognition, and the nature of educational system management. It is argued that assessment approaches within modern innovative educational technologies cannot be effectively aligned with traditional assessment systems. Today, the requirements for assessment extend beyond merely determining students' level of knowledge; they also include the formation of personal qualities, the development of independent learning skills, the stimulation of intrinsic interest, and the enhancement of motivation to achieve success. In this context, the effectiveness of criterion-referenced assessment is emphasized. In addition, the author presents examples of criterion-referenced assessment in physics, including problem solving, oral responses, practical and laboratory work, as well as assessment based on given topics.

Keywords: criterion, descriptor, competence, competitiveness, rubric, criterion-referenced assessment, validity, reliability.

In 2015, in order to ensure the civilized development of our country, the First President, within the 13th task of the program "Modernization of Kazakhstan: 20 Steps toward a Universal Labor Society," assigned a new task to the Ministry of Education and Science of the Republic of Kazakhstan, instructing it "to expand the use of interactive forms of education in the educational process of general secondary schools starting from the 2013–2014 academic year and to introduce special curricula for online learning" [1]. All of these measures represent actions being taken to counter the impact of political and economic instability occurring in the world on our country. In addition, global globalization and the rapid development of new technologies require all countries to reconsider the field of education and to seek effective ways of delivering education. Our young state should not remain on the sidelines of this issue. The education sector is the only sphere that develops continuously and requires constant improvement. A country's economy, culture, and overall development and prosperity all depend on this education sector. Therefore, both developed and developing countries around the world pay special attention to the development of human potential and human capital. The initial source, foundation, and core of human potential development are secondary and higher education institutions. Improving the quality of education in these institutions requires the development of clear measurement criteria for assessing students' achievements. This is because assessment occupies an important place in the educational process.

Assessment plays an important role not only in the educational process but also in a person's interaction with the surrounding social environment. Finding one's place in life depends on understanding one's own capabilities. In many cases, a person's awareness of their capabilities is formed through assessment based on criteria. By developing the skill of criterion-based assessment, a learner can later apply it to finding their place in society. In short, assessment is not only an integral part of the educational process, but also a process that plays a special role in a learner's life after leaving the educational institution. Therefore, involving students in the assessment process is very important.

At the present stage of school development, the emergence of the issue of changing or updating the system for assessing the quality of education is primarily caused by contradictions between changes in social demands and changes in students' cognition, as well as the nature of management of the education system. In addition, in traditional teaching, students' level of participation in the assessment process is low, and the assessment process is carried out unilaterally by teachers. Therefore, it is well known that assessment within modern innovative educational technologies cannot be harmonized with the old assessment system. Teaching that meets the demands of the time, with the widespread use of research activities, requires a new assessment system that corresponds to current requirements. A student must learn to analyze their own work, acquire experience in reflection, and be an active participant not only in the learning process but also in the assessment process. In this case, special attention

should also be paid to self-assessment and peer assessment. Assessing one's own work is, of course, more difficult than assessing the work of others; therefore, for a child to be able to give an appropriate assessment of their own work, they must know the work standards. These standards must be written in clear language and in such a way that they can demonstrate a concrete and fair assessment. Such an opportunity can be provided only by a modern assessment system—criterion-referenced assessment.

When recalling school years, most former students first remember the grades they received, especially the “two” (failing grade). Interestingly, they often claim that this grade was given unfairly and associate it with the teacher being in a bad mood or having an improper relationship with the teacher. Likewise, the “five” (excellent grade) received by others is associated with the student being the teacher's “favorite,” and that grade, too, is mentioned as having been given unfairly. Indeed, during traditional instruction, how are the grades “5” and “2” actually assigned? Who assigns them? Who can distinguish whether they are correct or objective? It is clear that everything comes down to one person—the teacher. The teacher compares the student's opinion, completed work, or oral response with their own ideal standard of work. Then the teacher begins to look for shortcomings in the student's work or response. If none are found, or if the teacher does not wish to find any, the student is given a “5”; if shortcomings are found, the grade is gradually reduced depending on their number. Sometimes, the grade is lowered or raised not based on the student's answer or solved problem, but on their behavior and conduct at school.

Many of us are well familiar with the dead silence that occurs during the break after teachers finish taking attendance and begin asking for homework, following the words “now to the blackboard...”. The fear and stressful state that arise at that moment in the minds of two-thirds of children are feelings very familiar to most of us. This was undoubtedly a situation that placed emotional pressure on students. Scientists even state that such emotional stress is comparable to the overload experienced by test pilots when they first fly new aircraft [2]. What exactly did the grade given on the basis of such answers measure and evaluate? In fact, during the Soviet period, teachers themselves could not independently establish the measures or criteria for grading. Such things came from higher authorities or were sent in the form of certain templates.

If we review the literature on these issues, the system of assessing educational quality and teaching and learning outcomes is considered through the concept of “balanced assessment,” which is widely used in schools in countries such as Singapore and England [3]. In traditional pedagogy, the concept of a grade is viewed one-sidedly as a qualitative indicator of the educational process. According to I. P. Podlasiy, a grade represents the relationship between actually mastered knowledge and skills and the knowledge and skills proposed for mastery [4]. According to A. K. Kolechenko, a teacher ensures a child's development at school not only through the subject content and teaching methods, but also through assessment

conducted with the participation of the student [5]. This corresponds to the modern understanding of assessment in pedagogy.

It has long been known, and in recent times has been increasingly discussed and written about, that the lack of fairness, validity, authenticity, and precision in grading, as well as the fact that grading lies within the authority of only one person, often leads school instruction to place students in stressful situations. Among the reasons for this are excessive workload in the tasks given to students, the teacher's authoritarian role, the mismatch of teaching methods with students' age characteristics, and many other factors. Among these, one of the foremost issues is the subjective assessment of students' work by teachers within “traditional” instruction. An incorrectly assigned, non-objective grade affects the entire educational process. If a student easily receives an “excellent” or “good” grade, their interest in learning decreases; if they receive a poor grade that does not correspond to their actual level, they may stop studying altogether. From this, it can be observed that assessing learning outcomes is one of the most important aspects of the educational process and that assessment plays a decisive role in the learning process.

The role of “assessment” in the learning process in preserving students' health and nervous system is attracting great interest among all teachers and parents. Here, the issue is not merely about replacing the five-point grading system with a six-, eight-, ten-, or hundred-point system; rather, the core issue lies in the correct assignment of grades. No matter how fair a grade may be considered, if students themselves do not participate in the assessment process, that grade remains one-sided and raises doubts about its fairness. Therefore, great importance is being given to involving students in assessment and, through social agreement between teachers and students, conducting assessment based on specific criteria—that is, criterion-referenced assessment. At present, a results-oriented education system places special emphasis on the quality of education. In turn, improving the quality of education requires the development of clear criteria for assessing students' achievements.

At the same time, the issue here is not only students' health; the grade that is given or will be given (regardless of how high it may be) should contribute to students' further progress. This is because learning and educational achievement have never had a final limit. Therefore, when a student receives the highest grade, they should not understand this as having reached the limit of learning, nor is such a situation possible. For this reason, it is appropriate for teachers and students to openly and jointly develop assessment criteria in the classroom through mutual agreement. In traditional teaching, the main requirement of grading is to determine a student's level and position in the learning process; however, although this requirement may be necessary, it cannot be considered sufficient under current conditions. Today, the requirement for grading is not limited to determining students' knowledge level, but also includes shaping their personal qualities, fostering independent learning, stimulating intrinsic interest, and developing motivation to achieve success.

The key to competitiveness also lies here. A distinctive feature of the modern education system is that its main product is competence—that is, the development, enhancement, and formation of learners' competence for certain types of activities. We must move from assessing students' knowledge, skills, and abilities to assessing the formation of their competencies. Pedagogical technologies and the assessment system play a significant role in developing students' competencies. This, in turn, requires a developmental orientation within the assessment system. The five-point grading system inherited from the Soviet era was designed primarily to raise students' level of knowledge; today, however, not only students' knowledge is central, but also the development of their competencies, personal qualities, appropriate interaction with the surrounding environment, self-development, and independent learning. This is precisely where the inadequacy of the traditional grading system currently in use lies.

By involving students in assessment, teachers help focus their attention on learning and guide them toward more precise and purposeful actions. Assessment should provide students with information that enables self-assessment and goal setting. In this regard, assessment through criteria is highly effective. When assessment criteria are set in advance, students can evaluate their level of goal attainment independently, without teacher intervention. For example, if achieving a certain level requires fulfilling three specific criteria, a student who overlooks one of these criteria will be uncertain about having achieved the learning objective, since the three criteria confirming the intended level have not been fully met. Therefore, it is very important for students to know by what means and how they will be assessed in order to achieve the goal. By regularly providing teachers with information about what they have learned and what they have not, students gradually develop the habit of jointly developing assessment criteria together with the teacher. This habit enables them to self-assess their level of goal attainment. When students are involved in the assessment process together with the teacher, they think at a higher level, because they evaluate their own learning that is necessary for both the educational process and life experience, and they gain greater opportunities to form competencies.

Involving students in the assessment process does not mean a one-sided notion that students themselves make the final decision about what needs to be learned or what should be assessed, or that they independently determine their own level of knowledge. By participating in assessment, students use the information accumulated as a result of assessment to manage their own learning and to find answers independently to questions such as how to improve

their learning, how to plan the next steps, and how to act in self-directed learning.

Through criterion-referenced assessment, students who are involved in the self-assessment process are able to identify the signs of successful learning. In this case, the teacher analyzes anonymous examples of students' strengths and the list of qualitative indicators that make them strong. At the same time, it is necessary to use evaluative frameworks to assess good work samples while explaining the pathways and conclusions for learning the qualities that lead to high achievement. By guiding students in assessment starting with one criterion and gradually expanding it to other directions, the teacher can increase the effectiveness of the process, create conditions for students to identify quality work samples, and contribute to their further development through self-evaluation of their own work. For example, students are given the opportunity to become familiar with, analyze, and evaluate sample works proposed by the teacher. They are encouraged to use criteria to improve the quality of sample works. They also learn to review and reconstruct the work sample themselves to improve it, or to provide suggestions and advice to the author of the sample work through a letter on how to improve the work. Such assessment approaches help students to revise their own work through self-support. By participating in the assessment process, students' intrinsic motivation for learning and goal orientation increase. This is because they engage in discussions with peers about their own development and share thoughts on how close they are to achieving success. They gain deeper self-knowledge, understand which material needs to be studied, and learn how to describe the quality of their own work. Criteria will not be useful unless students understand what these criteria mean in relation to their own work. Therefore, providing examples from students' work is one of the strategies for demonstrating the meaning of criteria in practice. Such examples should not be "ideal." Students learn better when they see work that is only slightly better than their current standard.

Criterion-referenced assessment is a process based on comparing students' learning achievements using clearly defined criteria that are aligned with educational goals and content, are known in advance to all participants in the educational process (students, school administration, parents, legal entities, etc.), and have been discussed collectively, thereby creating conditions for the formation of students' learning and cognitive competence [6]. A criterion is a rule, rationale, and indicator for making a decision about evaluating something in accordance with proposed requirements. Each criterion has a descriptor, which provides a clear explanation of the correctness of the outcome of performing a learning task. Assessment in accordance with the descriptor determines the extent to which a student has achieved their stated goal [6].

Table 1

**Criteria for Physical Problems
(for lower grades)**

№	Criteria	Descriptors	Points
1	Does not understand at all	1. Does not understand the given condition of the problem.	0
2	Remembers (satisfactory)	1. Knows which formula to use only in a memorized way.	5
		2. Cannot sufficiently understand the dependence of physical quantities on each other.	
		3. Does not know the units of measurement of physical quantities.	
		4. Makes mistakes in mathematical calculations.	
3	Understands (good)	1. Knows the units of measurement of physical quantities.	3
		2. Does not make mistakes in mathematical calculations	3
		3. Knows well which formula to use and can understand the dependence of physical quantities on each other.	4
		4. Cannot change the condition of the problem.	
4	Analyzes (very good)	1. Can complicate the problem by introducing new changes to the condition in order to deeply understand the physical phenomenon.	7
		2. Can evaluate the physical meaning of the problem.	8
Total			30

Table 2

Conversion of points into a traditional grade

Total points earned	Grade
0	«2»
5	«3»
5.1 – 15	«4»
15.1 – 30	«5»

Table 3

Criteria for Physical Problems

Section	Rubrics	Criteria	Descriptors	Points
A	Physics (knowledge and understanding)	1. Does not fully understand / understands the problem. Knows the units of measurement of the physical quantities given in the problem.	1. Does not understand the given condition of the problem. 2. Knows the given data of the problem and what needs to be found, but does not know which formula to use. 3. Knows which formula to use only in a memorized way. 4. Knows well which formula to use. 5. Does not know the units of measurement of physical quantities. 6. Knows the units of measurement of physical quantities.	
		2. Knows the formulas and laws necessary to solve the problem. Can derive the required formula using several laws.	1. Knows well which formula to use and the domain of its application, but cannot understand the dependence of physical quantities on each other. 2. Knows well which formula to use and can understand the dependence of physical quantities on each other. 3. Knows well which formula to use and understands the dependence of physical quantities on each other, but cannot derive the formula necessary to solve the problem. 4. Knows well which formula to use, understands the dependence of physical quantities on each other, and can derive the formula necessary to solve the problem.	

			5. Can solve a physical problem in several ways (methods, using different laws).	
		3. Explains the phenomenon by indicating the conditions under which it occurs and can change the condition of the problem.	1. Fully understands the physical meaning of the derived formulas, but does not correctly know their practical application. 2. Fully understands the physical meaning of the derived formulas and correctly knows their practical application. 3. Can construct similar problems by changing the condition of the problem. 4. Understands the interaction of bodies within a physical system with each other and with external objects, as well as the physical phenomena occurring in it.	
	Mathematics	1. Basic arithmetic operations. 2. Derivatives and differentiation. 3. Integrals.	3. 1. Even with support, the student is unable to perform basic mathematical operations. 2. The student shows limited understanding of mathematical operations and can perform them only with support. 3. The student finds an effective method for applying mathematical operations and solves them concisely. 4. The student solves a physical problem not only in the form of equations, but also using graphical or other representations.	
	Analysis	1. Can analyze the problem. 2. Can evaluate the problem. 3. Can change the conditions of the problem.	1. At the analysis stage, can answer questions about how identified physical quantities depend on other physical quantities and under what conditions these dependencies occur. 2. Can complicate the problem by introducing new changes to the condition in order to deeply understand the physical phenomenon. 3. Can evaluate the physical meaning of the problem.	

Table 4

Criteria for Assessing Oral Responses

Criteria	Descriptors	Points
Very good	a) Fully understands the physical meaning of the phenomena and laws under consideration; can prove knowledge of physical laws and theories by giving concrete examples, and can apply these laws and theories in new situations and in practical task performance.	26-30
	b) Knows precise definitions and explanations of basic concepts, laws, and theories; also knows the definitions of physical quantities, their units of measurement, and methods of measurement.	
	c) Correctly performs physical experiments, drawings, and schemes. Correctly writes formulas using the accepted system of symbols.	
	d) When answering, does not repeat the textbook text verbatim; highlights key ideas and concepts, provides justified personal opinions, and can relate new material in physics to previously studied material and to content from related subjects.	
	e) Can support the given answer with simple demonstration experiments.	
	f) Can form personal opinions, analyses, and conclusions on the given questions.	
	g) Can work independently and rationally with textbooks, supplementary literature, and reference materials.	

Good	a) Makes one minor error or no more than two overlooked points and can correct them independently or with slight assistance from the teacher.	18-25.9
	b) Has weak skills in working with reference literature (for example, can correctly find all required quantities and materials in reference sources, but works slowly).	
Satisfactory	Correctly understands the physical meaning of phenomena and laws, but when answering:	13-17.9
	a) Makes individual shortcomings in mastering key questions of the physics course that do not hinder further mastery of the curriculum material.	
	b) Experiences difficulties in solving different types of problems, explaining specific physical phenomena based on theories and laws, or applying theories to concrete practical examples.	
	c) Cannot fully answer the teacher's questions (or misses the main points), or does not sufficiently understand the essential meanings and merely repeats the content of the textbook.	
Threshold	d) When recounting the textbook text, does not sufficiently understand some important issues, or answers the teacher's questions with one or two serious errors.	0.1-12.9
	a) Does not know or understand the basic content of the curriculum material within the scope of the questions asked.	
	b) Or has weak mastery of the given material and does not fully understand it; moreover, cannot apply it to solve specific questions and tasks.	
Unsatisfactory	c) Or makes more than two serious errors in the given answer and cannot correct them even with the teacher's assistance.	0
	The student cannot answer any of the questions posed.	

Table 5

Conversion of Points into a Traditional Grade

Total points earned	Grade
0 – 12.9	«2»
13 – 17.9	«3»
18 – 25.9	«4»
26 – 30	«5»

The criteria for assessing oral responses can be used not only to evaluate how well a student has mastered the topic assigned as homework, but also to

clarify and assess a student's knowledge in various written tasks (scientific-research work, control and test problem solving, or laboratory work).

Table 6

Criteria for Assessing Practical and Laboratory Work

Criteria	Descriptors	Points
Very good	Performs measurements and experiments in full, observing the required sequence.	26-30
	Independently and consciously selects and prepares all equipment required for the experiment; all experiments are conducted under conditions that ensure high accuracy of the obtained results and conclusions.	
	All records, tables, drawings, diagrams, graphs, calculations, and conclusions are completed very neatly.	
	Correctly performs error analysis.	
	Fully complies with safety regulations.	
Good	Meets the requirements of the "Very good" criteria, and additionally the following conditions are met.	18-25.9
	The experiment is not conducted under conditions that fully ensure the required accuracy.	
	If 2–3 remarks are given, or one serious error and one remark are given.	

Satisfactory	Corresponds to the “Satisfactory” criterion if the work is not fully completed, but conclusions can be drawn from the completed part of the work, or if the following errors are made during measurements and experiments.	13-17.9
	Significant errors occur in the obtained results due to conducting the experiment in an unclear (irrational) manner.	
	If no more than two errors in total are made in calculations (in units in records, measurements, calculations, graphs, tables, diagrams, error analysis, etc.), and these errors are of an unclear nature but do not affect the final result of the work.	
	Error analysis is performed incorrectly or not performed at all.	
	The work is not fully completed, but the completed part allows correct results and conclusions to be drawn about the main, fundamental tasks of the work.	
Threshold	The work is not fully completed, and correct conclusions cannot be drawn from the completed part.	0.1-12.9
	Experiments, measurements, calculations, and observations are not performed correctly.	
	Several of the deficiency requirements specified for the “Satisfactory” criterion occur during the work and in the report.	
Unsatisfactory	The work is not completed, and correct conclusions cannot be drawn from the completed part.	0
	Experiments, measurements, calculations, and observations are not performed correctly.	
	Several of the deficiency requirements specified for the grade “3” occur during the work and in the report.	

If a student completes the work in an exemplary manner and approaches the performance of the work thoughtfully during the process, but nevertheless makes certain shortcomings, the teacher has the opportunity to assign a grade higher than the established norm.

The use of criterion-referenced assessment on the topic “Measuring the Capacitive Reactance of a Capacitor in an Alternating Current Circuit” [7].

Purpose of criterion-referenced assessment:

- not to evaluate only whether the student has completed the task and calculated correctly, but to assess the student’s understanding of the topic

“Measuring the Capacitive Reactance of a Capacitor in an Alternating Current Circuit” and their ability to apply knowledge gained from the laws of alternating current circuits to the acquisition of new knowledge;

- through this assessment, students can identify gaps in their knowledge and strive to achieve greater success in mastering the topic “Electromagnetic Oscillations”;

- to form students’ ability for self-assessment and to enable deep understanding of the material provided during the work process;

- to allow students to determine their level of mastery, the degree they have reached, and how they can move forward.

Table 7

Criterion		Highest level of students’ knowledge
C	Scientific-level knowledge and understanding	10
D	Scientific research methods and conducting experiments	10
E	Information analysis	10

Criterion	Students’ level of knowledge	Descriptors
C (max 10)	0	The student has not mastered any of the criteria listed below.
	1-2	From the topic “Alternating Electric Current,” the student can answer general questions, but cannot understand the full physical meaning.
	3-4	From the topic “Alternating Electric Current,” the student can answer general questions, but cannot understand the interdependence of some physical quantities.
	5-6	From the topic “Alternating Electric Current,” the student can answer general questions and fully understands the physical meaning, but does not correctly know its practical application.

	7-8	The student can correctly analyze and compare, and can identify the role of physical quantities in this process, but cannot present them properly.
	9-10	The student can fully (explain) the topic. Can work independently at a scientific level. Has good command of physical instruments and can conduct experiments.
D (max 10)	0	The student has not mastered any of the criteria listed below.
	1-2	The student could not fully complete the work because they do not know some physical laws.
	3-4	The student knows physical laws, but could not complete the work correctly because they could not properly distinguish physical quantities.
	5-6	The student knows physical laws and physical quantities, but could not apply them during the experiment.
	7-8	The student has fully mastered the topic "Alternating Electric Current," but during the experimental work could not correctly reveal some physical processes.
	9-10	The student has fully mastered the topic "Alternating Electric Current," correctly performed the experimental work, and fully demonstrated the physical process. Knows how the knowledge gained in determining the capacitance of a capacitor in an alternating current circuit can be used in future scientific work.
E (max 10)	0	The student has not mastered any of the criteria listed below.
	1-2	While performing the work, the student could not understand the readings of the instruments. The calculation results are incorrect. Does not know the units of physical quantities (v , I_m , U_m , C , X_c).
	3-4	While performing the work, the student correctly records the instrument readings, but cannot use the formulas from the topic "Alternating Electric Current."
	5-6	While performing the work, the student correctly records the instrument readings and uses the formulas from the topic "Alternating Electric Current," but makes a mathematical error in the calculations.
	7-8	While performing the work, the student correctly records the instrument readings, correctly performs the calculations using formulas from the topic "Alternating Electric Current," but cannot explain them properly.
	9-10	While performing the work, the student correctly records the instrument readings, correctly performs the calculations using formulas from the topic "Alternating Electric Current," and explains them correctly.

Table 8

Conversion of Scores into a Traditional Grade

Total points earned	Grade
0 – 12.9	«2»
13 – 17.9	«3»
18 – 25.9	«4»
26 – 30	«5»

Table 9

Criteria for Assessing Control and Independent Written Work

Criteria	Descriptors	Points
Very good	Assigned for work completed without errors and without remarks.	26 – 30
Good	The work is fully completed, but: a) one non-serious error and one remark are present, b) or two remarks are present.	18 – 25.9
Satisfactory	If the student correctly completes half of the work, or if: a) the number of serious errors does not exceed two, b) the number of serious errors and remarks does not exceed one, c) the number of serious errors does not exceed two or three, d) there is one serious error and no more than three remarks, e) there are no serious errors, but 4–5 remarks are present.	13 – 17.9
Threshold	If the number of serious errors and remarks exceeds the norm set for the “Satisfactory” criterion, or if less than half of the work is completed correctly.	0.1 – 12.9
Unsatisfactory	The student does not begin the work or completes only 10% of the given task, that is, writes the condition of the task using generally accepted symbolic notation.	0

A teacher may assign a grade higher than the established “norm” if the student’s completed work is exemplary.

Table 10

Conversion of Scores into a Traditional Grade

Total points earned	Grade
0 – 12.9	«2»
13 – 17.9	«3»
18 – 25.9	«4»
26 – 30	«5»

The following are considered serious (gross) errors:

- lack of knowledge of basic concepts, laws, rules, fundamental theories, formulas, symbols denoting physical quantities, and their units of measurement;
- lack of knowledge of the names of units of measurement;
- inability to identify the main idea in an answer;
- inability to apply one’s knowledge to solving problems and explaining physical phenomena;
- inability to summarize and generalize the work;
- inability to construct and read schematic diagrams and graphs;
- inability to prepare equipment or a physical apparatus, inability to conduct experiments, incorrect calculations, or inability to draw conclusions from the obtained results;
- inability to work with textbooks or reference materials in physics and technology;
- violation of technical safety rules during physical experiments;

- careless handling of laboratory equipment and measuring instruments.

Non-serious (minor) errors include:

- formulations, definitions, concepts, laws, and theories do not fully cover the essential characteristics of the defined concepts; lack of precision;
- errors made when recording readings of measuring instruments, not related to determining the value of a scale division;
- errors arising from failure to observe the operating conditions of experiments and measuring instruments (e.g., incorrect positioning of scales, incorrect choice of reference system);
- errors caused by inaccuracies in conventional symbols in schematic diagrams and in graphs;
- poorly thought-out methods of solving tasks or insufficiently planned oral responses (violation of logic, replacement of main questions with secondary ones);
- lack of accuracy in methods of working with reference and other literature, inability to solve a problem in a general form.

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